

REWRITING OF SOCIAL CONNECTIONS AND INTERACTIONS AT THE BOUNDARY OF THREATS OF IDEOLOGICAL ENCLAVIZATION

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Summary

The changes taking place at the level of communities, professional groups or debates networks allow the storage, interpretation and use of some communication patterns on whose basis definitions of group behaviors may configure. The network profile analyses oriented psychosociological researches allow qualitative leap at the level of identification of some adjacency matrixes emphasizing the interactions of the factors involved in information flows. In approaching this topic we start from the hypothesis that the understanding of the functioning mechanisms of these flows represents the first borderline of knowing and forecasting of some identity conflicts which may escalate. Related to this we aim to highlight the fact that the identity tensions occurred against the background of global mutations are doubled by the evolution of capacity of collective imaginary of systematically configuring forms of aggressive representation. In this dense territory from cultural and social point of view touched by the perspective of linguistic particularities and religious customs, the challenge is represented by the potential reflex of self-isolation, ethnicization and ideological enclavization in direct confrontation with the attributes of integration and cooperation within the European space.

Key words: *social dynamics; centrality, connectiveness, permissiveness; communication, destructuring; ideology.*

Introduction

The indicators proving a certain acceleration of the social dynamics (they can be closely linked to the speed of innovation of the means of communication and the increased capacity to diversify the means of communication). The virtual environment obliges the global society to simplify the platforms and means of communication. As technology becomes more complex and efficient, the use interface is simplified, offering the software user advantages never offered by last generations.

Along with this entire process, we notice how the usual flow of words is completed by universal terms, operations identification formulas, message encrypting formulas, various associations of symbols and channeled ideas – an entire mnemotechnical language with which the world's state of mind seems to be rewritten. Nevertheless, the persons singularize, withdraw in the impenetrable shell of an identity reconfiguration, hiding behind avatars of some false profiles adapted to thematic requirements claimed by registering within social media. Behind multiple identities, the person disappears and individualities appear, rather false, unpersonal group

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individualities, who do not assume the word's responsibility or more precisely do not assume the consequences of a certain flow of information and ideas. In the shadow of anonymity, there are created various dialogic platforms, informational connections where scenarios generating speculative transacting principles, disinformation and even states of conflicting states are working.

1. Mutations occurred in the lines of interhuman communication

The facilities offered by online social platforms Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram and others, allowing a particularly complex interaction between participations located in different corners of the world, reduce the distances between humans and shortens the communication time. The creation of debates networks, discussions forums, information circuits represent a huge advantage with regard to interaction and exchange of knowledge. The internet – built as an exceptional informational source is actually a virtual space storing resources of ideas, knowledge and data which may be exploited by the users within the platforms of professional collaboration. The instant messaging, weblogs, data administration and network management software are used in the business, socializing, educational areas, but – very important – there are continuously used also in the area of hybrid war, informational war as well as in the area of mediatic war.

The blogging, online communities, fan-clubs, reaction groups, social activism forums – for example – do not represent only opportunities for maintaining some platforms of personal or group representation or some debate medias, but they also represent as many territories for information testing, reactions research and shaping and ideological vectorization. In case of socializing, "The Stakeholder Concept" is not used only within the meaning of extending a circle of discussions, but is especially dedicated to the development of a strategic planning of some ideological packages with conducted effects.

The analysis of social networks is a technical option providing the researchers of virtual environment with a series of descriptive statistics related to constituting of those complex information flows involving humans, groups, organizations, hardware as well as other entities processing information and knowledge to be used in specialized platforms or for constructing and building the opinion. The advantage of extending a circle based on a social network making more nodes and connections is represented by the large volume of network entries and by a better data flow as well as by a better resolution of the representation profiles. This network analysis, interpretation and modelling mechanism transforms internet into a weapon used in the most singular and secluded spots on the planet.

Things evaluate to an absolutely uncontrollable sense in the area of hidden internet (Deep Web), where the online traffic monitoring mechanisms are already occulted in the area of using some Tor type browsers. In the name of liberty of virtual environment browsing under an anonymous identity, as reaction to any form of network monitoring threatening the intimacy of the person, the private life and the personal liberties, the solution of some shielded communications offers multiple possibilities of developing a criminal environment. Therefore, the internet is not used only as a source of ideological inspiration or network building catalysator, but also for getting information on models of weapons or other information of fight techniques or methods².

The sociometric analysis, the ones connecting the data of sociology with its mathematical representations allows the creation – on the basis of functional algorithms – of some virtual connections between users, with social, commercial, political and educational applications. The collecting and registration of analysis units, which are technical integrated into processes of research of relations between individuals or groups at the level of socializing nodes, imply the

² Anghel Andreescu, PhD Professor; Nicolae Radu, PhD Associate Professor: Terrorist Organizations, Artprint Publishing House, Bucharest, 2008, p. 136.

functioning and instrumentalization of some network phenomena such as *connectivity* and *centrality*. The centrality degree of a network node represents the fluidity rate of a dense or less dense connected node.

One of the software offering the definition of centrality degree of a network node is UCINET 6.0., a software built on the formula of some tables intersecting within an adjacency matrix.

*"In UCINET 6.0, the entire data is configured inside the matrix. While the requests and results of some procedures may reflect the language most commonly associated with this technique (of measuring the centrality of "relations"), it is extremely important that the user maintains a "matrix focused" data image. The entire UCINET data is eventually stored and describes various collections of matrixes. The understanding of the way in which graphs, networks, relations, hypergraphs and all other entities of network analysis are represented as matrixes is essential for the efficient use of the system"*³.

The user of this specialized software for analyzing the social networks must have at disposal a repository of labels or key words or phrases used for investigating the matrix. The definitions and reports of this investigation highlight both the network profile as well as major details regarding the moral, professional character, competence or good faith of involved factors.

The challenges posed in the virtual space by cybercrime involves a more applied role of the frame of judicial regulation in this field, intended to protect the communications and data flow. We indicate the fact that such a regulation frame was adopted at international level by Budapest Convention on Cybercrime⁴. Beyond any permissivity, the simplification of use interfaces of online working platforms, the innovation of some new communication ways as well as the opening of mass access to communication gadgets involve the major risks of penetration in the informational market of ideological instrumentations or instrumentations of terrorist nature. Besides this, each software or gadget user – starting from (now) simple android to graphic station or quantic computer – must know the risk of exposure to this kind of facilities.

2. Social connections and interactions. Group stereotypes and prejudices

The theme of *social identity* anchored in the need of legitimacy and affirmation of values involves the tools of another identity category, namely *social representation*. In this representation environment, in response to uniformization of cultures and facilities of global communication, makes its appearance the trend of ideological self-isolation, ethnicization and enclavization of some social groups. This trend, appeared in social environment, introduces in the social-cultural exchange market the adversity reaction to globalization. Nevertheless, to mark the definition of causality relations established in this immense system of social determination, in the absence of some gnoseologic shift allowing the precise correspondence between events and significance, is a difficult measure.

The world of political commentators, analysts and political experts is chained in the gear of some interactions showing the world the entire range of possibilities as result of dialogue. These possibilities are not necessarily connected to the structure of linguistic valences, but to the force of some argumentations reduced to the level of mutual constraints⁵. For a consecrated political commentator, the persuasion resides not only in the tone of approach, but also in the quality of the

³ Stephen P Borgatti; Martin G Everett; Linton C Freeman: „UCINET 6.0 for Windows. Software for social network analysis”, *USER'S GUIDE, 0.5 Matrix Orientation*. Ed. by Analytic Technologies, Harvard, 2002, p.6

⁴ Anghel Andreescu, PhD Professor; Nicolae Radu, PhD Associated Professor: *Islamic Jihad – from Defeat of Terror and Holy War to Hope of Freedom*, Codex Publishing House, Bucharest, 2008, p. 319

⁵ Webb Keane, „Semiotics and the social analysis of material things”, in *Language & Communication*, edited by Department of Anthropology, LSA Building, University of Michigan, USA, no. 23 /2003 [409–425], p. 412

expressed content. The limit up to which we can talk about an informative content, beyond which the information transforms into an ideologization instrument, going through various interpretation techniques, is a one difficult to notice. In the communication act, the body of prejudices prevails over the body of suppositions and opinions, which in most cases, transforms a debate into an inconsistent moment of reflection over cognitive capacities of the previous speakers and not over approached content.

If for exercising personal opinions it coexists a „minimum required” prejudices, as regards the gearing of group opinion, the prejudices manifest to an amplitude specific to raising to a power. The group prejudice represents the subject most studies in social psychology. The trend of individuals *of identity with the group to which they belong or the trend of identifying with certain attributes which are relevant to the group*⁶, belongs to a social category to be investigated. In a study initiated in the field of social psychology, Francesco La Barbera proves the fact that an efficient educational strategy may positively influence the group perception and reaction with regards to certain research topics. The knowledge of certain communication related elements, as well as the knowledge of some elements related to identification of discrimination targets, deconstructing and correct analyzation of group stereotypes have a significant effect on reducing the manifestation rate of group prejudices as well as of group partiality.

The nature of transparent investigation itself as well as the nature of consciousness of the aspects related to discrimination, negative social stereotypes, group prejudices or inter-group ideologic conflicts substantially eliminate the distance between the two sides. The study to which we refer has proven the unpredictable character, from the social point of view, of a massive migration causing deep social and economic changes as well as sufficiently proven reactions to the radical changes of society. There was established that the discrimination of immigrants is a reaction of social response to a category considered as being a competition category on the local market of jobs. Another social impediment reflected in the local public mind was established to be the ethnic and linguistic identity affiliation itself, the need of this competition category of protecting its own social identity and to manifest, from the cultural and religious point of view, inside the groups to which they belong.

The mechanisms generating group stereotypes and prejudices in relation to immigrants or the stereotypes and prejudices appeared in immigration communities related to host countries are ultimately based on a real inter-group competition for incompatible purposes, creating a negative interdependence between these categories of groups. In case of establishing some upstream targets, promoting a positive interdependence, the character of relation becomes a positive one.

Within the study, there have been especially investigated the mechanisms for generating and promoting positive reactions by including some messages of high moral motivation in the relation calculation between involved factors. The analysis of reactions indicated that the *high motivation condition* is the key of the positive effect reflecting on the entire relation spectrum and on all involved subjects. The effect proposed by message modelling was directly felt not only at emotional level, but also significantly proved the improvement of inter-group relations⁷. It proves the fact that the social dynamics built on the basis of some educational solutions thought in the knowledge sphere of social psychology could recalibrate the relations between humans, anchoring them in category of positive motivations appropriate to some common social interests.

⁶ Francesco La Barbera, „Educating to Tolerance: Effects of Communicating Social Psychology Research Findings” in *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 2015, Vol. 11(3), p. 476

⁷ Francesco La Barbera, „Educating to Tolerance: Effects of Communicating Social Psychology Research Findings” , in *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 2015, Vol. 11(3), 476–483

3. Ideologization threats

For a better understanding of distinction between the role of religious ideology leaving its mark on the cultural space and the role of spirituality activating the private resorts of emotion and moral elevation, we shall use the «torch» model, asserting being inspired by Antoine de Saint-Exupery that: „*The virtue of the candle lies not in the wax that leave its trace, but in its light*”⁸.

The identity interactions induced by the phenomenon of a globalization changing the dominant world map, redefining of social-political order as well as repositioning in the project of some diplomatic and military force which are about to make decisions among the most dramatic and spectacular ones, lead to conclusion that the world in which we live is a world becoming more and more unsafe.

Starting from the pretext that the modern world is the product of the decay caused by abandoning traditions, Aleksandr Dughin, Russian geopolitician, engages in an extremely passionate political debate with the Brazilian philosopher Olavo de Carvalho, a polemic debate materialized in *United States and the New World Order*, recently published by Humanitas Publishing House⁹. The two are the exponents of two adverse ideologies touching only in the interpretation points of the same phenomena. In return, both the firm irreconciliation as well as the divergence with regard to contouring of arguments provide the characteristic note of this intense dialogue. The debate was held online in March – July 2011, being mediated by organizers Giuliano Morais and Ricardo Almeida from Brazil, who also signed the preface of the book. For us, this debate represents an important source of understanding the points of doctrine anchorage, both by one side as well as by the other side of the ideological spectrum in media confrontation.

In the context of carrying out by Russia of some military exercises for intimidation purpose, on the background of Crimea annexation and expansion of the presence in Donetk Ukraine province, the political, diplomatic and military tensions regarding the situation of Black Sea area are continuously escalating. To this adds also the intention of Russia to extend towards Europe, targeting at an economic alliance, but, moreover, a political support of some European countries, such as Germany and France, countries becoming more vulnerable as a result of migration wave and Islamic terrorism.

The debate of the two geopoliticians reveals the political, ideological and economical factors and actors currently defining the dynamics and configuration of the power in the world¹⁰, but moreover, it shows the profound substrate of the political and ideological debate regarding global events. This form of dialogue – sometimes polemic – highlights mechanisms of thinking of some conceptual blocks insidiously anchored in the socializing environment.

Surprisingly appears the speech of the Russian ideologist Dughin with regards to cultural and spiritual geopolitics of modern Russia, which, in his opinion, must be based on a doctrine, called „*The Forth Political Theory*” extracting what he considers good from **liberalism**, **communism** and national socialism or **fascism**, to give way to the ideological doctrine called **national Bolshevism**. In his opinion, this *forth political theory* would represent: „*socialism without materialism, atheism, progressivism and modernism*”, completed by „*fascism free of racism or nationalism*”¹¹. Quite strange is the statement of the same Russian ideologue: „*I sincerely believe that a forth political theory, national-bolshevism and eurasiatism may be of great help for our*

⁸ classical citation – Antoine de Saint-Exupery, in Citatepedia, available at: <http://www.citatepedia.ro/index.php?id=18078> – accessed on 11. 08. 2019, in the author’s translation.

⁹ Olavo De Carvalho ~ Aleksandr Dughin; *United States and New World Order* – translation from Portuguese by Simina Popa & Cristina Nițu, Humanitas Publishing House, Bucharest, 2016.

¹⁰ Olavo De Carvalho ~ Aleksandr Dughin, *United States and New Order...*, p.7

¹¹ Ibidem, p. 245, in the author’s translation.

nations, our countries and our civilizations”¹². According to citation of De Carvalho, the Russian geopolitician would have affirmed in an interview published in *Fronde* publication, the astounding idea that „nothing makes him more sad that the fact that Hitler and Stalin did not join to destroy France, England and everything that they would meet in their way, sharing the entire universe the benefits already made known to the ones from Gulag and Auschwitz”¹³. These extremely dangerous affirmations, made online or in the web undergrounds by army of trolls of Kremlin represent the indicator of a militant-aggressive policy which does not take into consideration the civilizational and cultural evolutions of Modernity.

In another context, Aleksandr Dughin, declares himself as supporter of the Orthodox Tradition and affirms: „If there are real traditional values in their fundamentals (and surely there are), we will save them only by means of **process of global destruction** of Modernity”¹⁴. Under the access of the same ideological crisis, impregnated by a doctrine of destruction, the ideologist Dughin affirms: „The American Empire should be destroyed. At it will be (destroyed) at a certain moment [...] I am firm against modernist and postmodernist essentially occidental values and which are promulgated by United States...”¹⁵. „The fight of Russian-Chines militancy and Muslim Brotherhood against Occident, USA and globalization is a just and proper cause, which should be supported by all citizens of the world!”¹⁶.

We stop here as regards these references, considering that they succeed in shaping, without any other comment, the picture of *interpretation exaltation*¹⁷ of this illustrious political advisor of President Putin, an Eurasian-bolshevist ideologist whose ideas deeply advance towards grasping some authority pivots belonging to various university environments, located in neighboring countries of Russian Federations. Moreover, knowing the force of social anchoring of religiosity, such an ideologization is diffusely conducted towards ecclesial environment, towards church communities and forums belonging to Orthodox specific countries or towards debates communities inside Russian diaspora living in Occident.

In response, professor Olavo de Carvalho has a meticulous, surgical and absolutely essential intervention, succeeding in providing a pertinent analysis of Dughin ideology representing the basis of the current Russian imperialist initiatives: „Prof. Dughin, who does not seem to conceive another model of social control besides Russian imperial theocracy, in which politics and Church (and later the party) act hand in hand for subjugating the nation, considers United States of America as a «selva selvaggia» [wild forest] of egoisms in conflict, proving that he does not know anything about American life”¹⁸. Carvalho claims that the national-bolshevist project of Dughin, with its Eurasian version results from a contradiction of Russian imperial religion. He affirms that this political ideology reflects a structural internal drama of the Orthodox Church¹⁹ which may be captive to this Eurasian project, transforming into an instrument in the hands of Russian secret services²⁰.

The evolution of this dialogue reveals the amazing capacity of ideological – religious doctrine of overcoming by means of socializing instruments within the spiritual frame of some traditional communities. Such an ideology bears in its subsidiary the nostalgic coordinates of the reconfiguration of the sphere of influence of the Russian state in Europe, given that the Russian Federation and state actors within the European Union carry on important commercial relations. In

¹² Ibidem, p. 249, in the author’s translation.

¹³ Ibidem, p. 150, in the author’s translation.

¹⁴ Ibidem, p. 145, in the author’s translation.

¹⁵ Ibidem, p. 242, in the author’s translation.

¹⁶ Ibidem, p. 71, in the author’s translation.

¹⁷ Ibidem, p. 150, in the author’s translation.

¹⁸ Ibidem, p. 117, in the author’s translation.

¹⁹ Ibidem, p. 127.

²⁰ Olavo De Carvalho ~ Aleksandr Dughin, *United States and New Order ...*, pp. 157-158.

this context the aversion of the ideologue Dughin towards the European civilizational modernity, as well as his universalist-Bolshevik vision are difficult to fit into a certain coherence of meaning.

4. Configuration of institution of power in the European cooperation and integration space

The platforms of some international agreements prepared before the moment of «Iron Curtain» fall²¹, stating the observance of human rights and fundamental freedoms, including the freedom of thinking, consciousness, religion or political belief, without discriminations regarding race, gender, language or religion belong to area of normality of observing some legitimate rights. The final act of *Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe*, held in Helsinki on 1st of August 1975²², represents the base needed for appearing in Europe of a space for integration and cooperation in the field of some cultural, linguistic, ethnic and religious exchanges which shall later lead to shaping of a certain type of cultural division and appearance of some ideological and political syntheses based on ethnicity and religious affiliation. There must be taken into consideration, within this meaning, the existence of some European autonomies, like Germans in Wallonia, Faeroe minority in Faeroe Islands – autonomous towards Denmark, Aland Island independent towards Finland, Tirol Germans in South Tirol – autonomous towards Italy and other regions: French from Vallée d'Aoste, minority of Friuli from Friuli-Venezia Giulia region from Italy, Basque Country and Galicia and community Valencia in Spain etc. All these represent as many attempts to keep a certain level of self-governing, which, besides the enlarged administrative and political autonomy, involve also special linguistic, cultural, educational rights having as purpose the conservation and development of the culture and identity of minority.

As an expression of a certain reflex of atomization and separation, we find in Europe certain tendencies of division and breaking of the patterns of unity, some starting from the pretext of ethnicity, others starting from religious pretexts. We mention here the independence movement from Spain of the autonomous region of Catalonia, the phenomenon of the dismemberment of Yugoslavia – divided primarily on the basis of religious conflict, centrifugal movements and manifestations of autonomy of some regions, a series of tendencies that reflect the misunderstanding of the unional political vision as well as the valences of the European Union.

Taking into account the issue of the relaxation of the relations between nations and people, regarding the assurance of peace in Europe, or the aspects regarding the sovereign equality of the people, the economic cooperation between the states, as well as the problem of developing and amplifying the course of building confidence and making commitments related to ensuring security and defense, the European space is a space of coexistence provided by specific agreements and specified legal regulations.

The facilities of global communication reduce the time of mobilizing the ideologization vectors. The virtual space represents the operability platform of ideologization and mediatic conduct. The most initiatives of destructuring and atomization and influence spheres are online. The global community space makes place to the dark perspective of autonomization and ideological enclavization.

On the other side, there is noticed the fact that the community space, cleared of the function of instinct of conservation of national stratifications, does no longer rely that much on the role and support of state entities, but is perpetually based on the logic of institutional consolidation. The

²¹ «Iron Curtain» is a syntagma often used for designating the line in Europe between Western Europe and Eastern Europe during Cold War.

²² Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe – Final Act, Helsinki, 1975, p. 6 available at: <http://www.osce.org/helsinki-final-act?download=true> - accessed on 05. 10. 2016

constitutional order of states makes place to *institutional* order. The confrontation between ethnic regionalism and cosmopolite regionalism, approached by Christian Giordano, succeeds in being the new paradigm of united Europe.

Besides the cosmopolite profile of social determinations, Ch. Giordano makes the distinguish regarding the trend of resuscitating the ethnic regionalism. This is characterized by social-political efforts of building a collectivity whose common belief is based on ethnical criteria, considered as being sole qualities for group affiliation, such as origin, ancestors, history, traditions, culture, religion, language and – not at last – territory²³.

Totally agreeing with the set of consequences of gradual loss of sovereignty of national, sovereign states, whose projects of aggregation try to pass beyond the limited range of current political borders, such as beyond the pretended ethnic-cultural homogeneity, Giordano affirms that this would be the ideal type of regionalism, at the extreme opposed to ethnic regionalism²⁴. At this moment, as we do not have an alternative for exploring this relation, we admit the possibility of a communication between heterogeneous identities without eliminating the distinct identities.

5. Guarantees related to right of coexistence of all ethnic, cultural and religious categories in the community space. Confusion of ethnicization, isolation and enclavization.

As a result of migratory flows from Orient to Occident – started even from last century, the European space ended of being a space of ethnicity, as it is a space of a strong internal dynamics. This is the reason why aspects related to multiculturalism, religious and linguistic diversity are the subject of some regulations within community documents and conventions:

Article 9 of European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms²⁵ guarantees the freedom of thinking, freedom of conscience and religious freedom. In the two paragraphs of the article there is highlighted the fact that this right includes also the freedom of religious manifestation within a public or private worship, alone or with communion with others, or the liberty of opting from changing religious beliefs and religion in general.

These freedoms are subject of provisions of Laws protecting the rights and freedoms of others, the public order, moral and health. The Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, known also under the name of European Convention on Human Rights, was sign in Rome, on 4th of November 1950 by twelve member states of European Council and entered into force on 03rd of September 1953. Until 1st of June 2010, its text was subject of several changes, adding and amendments.

The Christianity predominant in Europe, characterized by pluriconfessionalism (Catholicism, Orthodoxy, Protestantism, Neo-Protestantism) has given way to impact of religious pluralism freely manifesting in the European space. The status granted to religions, cults and confessions as well as non-confessional organizations within the Union is regulated by Declaration no. 11 of the Treaty of Amsterdam²⁶ related to Churches and non-confessional Organizations. The text of this declaration indicates the fact that at the level of European Union, the status of Churches and religious communities is respected under the conditions provided by national legislation of

²³ Christian Giordano, Ethnic versus Cosmopolitan Regionalism? in *Ethnologia Balkanica*, (Region, Regional Identity and Regionalism in Southeastern Europe – part I) vol. 11, Editor: Klaus Roth, Ulf Brunnbauer, by InASEA, Germany, 2007, p. 50.

²⁴ *Ibidem*

²⁵ European Convention on Human Rights [as amended by Protocols N^o. 11 and N^o. 14; supplemented by Protocols N^{os}. 1, 4, 6, 7, 12 and 13], European Court of Human Rights, Council of Europe, F-67075 Strasbourg cedex: available at: http://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf - accessed on 5. 10. 2016

²⁶ Treaty of Amsterdam amending the Treaty on European Union, European Communities, Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, Luxembourg, 1997, available at: <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/treaty/pdf/amst-en.pdf> - accessed on 5. 10. 2016

member states as well as the fact that the philosophical status of non-confessional organizations is respected as well.

The matter of guaranteeing the freedom of thinking, the freedom of conscience and the religious freedom is to be found within *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*²⁷, in Article 10. Article 21 of the above-mentioned Charter contains references to non-discrimination based on religious affiliation or option. This article prohibits "any discrimination based on genetic, language, religion, political beliefs or opinion characteristics or characteristics of other nature, such as sex, gender, race, color, ethnicity, nationality, social origin, affiliation to a minority, property, birth, disability or age of someone".

A wider regulation frame is offered by Article 22 of this community document, reminding the fact that the Union shall respect the cultural, religious and linguistic diversity and thus the forms and means of expression of this diversity.

The way of coexistence of all ethnic, cultural, religious categories is the subject of research of some academic networks taking into consideration all sides of the problem. International Migration, Integration and Social Cohesion (IMISCOE)²⁸ reunites prestigious researchers in the field of cultural and linguistic diversity.

The research group of "Cultural, religious and linguistic diversity" within IMISCOE network is the one setting as target the approach of key aspects of diversity theme, as reflected in the engagements of policies at national level and public debates. The purpose of this research group consists in obtaining an overall view related to context of approach, both in debating environment as well as in specialty literature.

The research is intended to indicate the main trends and themes circumscribing to problem of cultural, religious and linguistic diversity and the respective themes debates reflect the various contributions of researches from an interdisciplinary perspective²⁹.

The assimilation of ethnic minorities is designed as a period of adjustment, a waiting time for the migrants to give up to their traditional practices and adopt the social integration way of majority. But, in different countries, strong movements of assimilation rejection were created in the name of respecting the rights of minorities to identity and in the name of respecting the ethnic specificities.

Starting on '70s, the societies confronting with significant influxes of migrants have admitted the principle of tolerance related to minority ethnics, providing them with the right to representation and group participation, with the rights related to expressing the cultural identity – including the freedom of association, the freedom of faith manifesting, the freedom of speaking own language and the freedom of holding an own material and cultural patrimony. On the background of public sensitiveness to anti-discrimination and anti-racism, the promotion of these identity subjects within governing policies, have led to the configuration of a strong "recognition"

²⁷ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, (2000/C 364/01), Official Journal of the European Communities, 18.12.2000, available at: http://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf - accessed on 5. 10. 2016

²⁸ IMISCOE – (www.imiscoe.org) constitutes one of the most important «Excellency networks» from Europe, being supported on the basis of the sixth Framework Program of European Commission for Research and Development (2002-2006). At European level, it is the largest network of researchers in the field of migration and integration. This involves the scientific activity of more than 500 scientists from all over Europe, organized in research groups at the level of 36 member institutes. It is an organizational structure focused on comparative research, granting of prizes, preparing of some communications as well as involving the students in the process of doctoral building. The IMISCOE annual conferences have become a key element in the agenda of majority of researches in the field of migration and integration. The network publishes different book series and *Comparative Migration Studies* magazine.

²⁹ Steven Vertovec; Susanne Wessendorf, Migration and Cultural, Religious and Linguistic Diversity in *Europe: An overview of issues and trends*, - Working Paper No. 18 - Centre on Migration, Policy and Society, University of Oxford, 2005.

political strand of minorities originating from migration flow. The linguistic and religious diversity subordinated to the conditions of the larger sphere of multiculturalism.

The policy of majority, of accepting and recognizing the diversity, cannot encourage the confusion of some minority accents of ethnicization, social isolation and enclavization. The legitimate trend of ethnic groups of highlighting specific cultural values, impregnating their cultural and spiritual life, does not exonerate these groups neither from social integration and observing laws and law enforcement nor from showing respect towards cultural and spiritual values of the host countries.

Conclusions

The idea of multiculturalism cannot express isolation and segmentation of society into linguistic and ethnic cultural specificities, it is not a disjunction of ideological consideration intended to socially and morally fragment, but it is also a form of cultural legitimacy in the concert of a diversity tempered by legitimacy of harmony and complementarity.

The statistics indicate the fact that the groups of immigrants belonging to second or third generation tend towards residential self-isolation and self-segregation, have a low education level, have an increased unemployment rate, a general standard of living tending towards pauperization, a fact directly reflected in the low quality of housing and extremely low indexes of economic and professional mobility³⁰. The evolutions of adaptability forms or more precisely the stagnation shown at the level of this European social diachronism pose serious adequacy problems.

On the background of this structural isolation of the migrant populations massively entering Europe starting with the autumn of year 2015 until today, the Christian faith of Europe is subject of variously worries. These worries expressed even during the leadership of Pope Benedict XIV, when Vatican signaled the risk of an imminent Islamization of Europe are also today perfectly valid. In an interview for German weekly newspaper *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, G. Ganswein, the Pope's private secretary has drawn the attention on the fact that the Occident is threatened by Islamization, emphasizing the fact that Europe does not have to give up to its Cristian roots³¹. The European space remains nevertheless a space of civilizing resources, capable of resisting to changes and mutations within society. The social networks, the online forums, the opinion vectors and media platforms can increasingly assume the role of some debates correctly highlighting the defense mechanisms against the ideologic offensive and dedicatedly confront the initiatives of disintegration and enclavization based on ethnic and religious criteria of communities and groups. A more appropriate knowledge of group specificity is required, but also a better precision regarding the mediatization of legislative formulates guaranteeing the European community climate.

The stakes of Islamic migration taken into consideration for German or Scandinavian demographic revival or for the demographic revival of other European areas weakened by the deficit of natality indexes below the level of mortality index, constitute an offer which is not pretty safe, as long as these group are denied from inside the access to modernity. The effort of integration shall be evaluated depending on the amount of risks reported to costs of their elimination.

When we talk about a lot of emigrants crossing the European free passing zone, we cannot a priori consider that we are facing a mass of radical Muslims only, capable of blowing up the European social peace at any time. Nevertheless, we may be cautious and rigorously research to what extent the temptation of ethnic, cultural or religious *specificity mobilization* may affect in any way the peace of the European continent or the peace of the entire world.

³⁰ Steven Vertovec; Susanne Wessendorf, Migration and Cultural, Religious and Linguistic Diversity in Europe: An overview of issues and trends, - Working Paper No. 18 - Centre on Migration, Policy and Society, University of Oxford, 2005, p. 13.

³¹ Anghel Andreescu, PhD Professor; Nicolae Radu, PhD Associated Professor: Terrorist Organizations, Artprint Publishing House, Bucharest, 2008, p. 69

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